

Field screening of rice varieties against gall midge and rice tungro virus

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In the national screening nursery of kharif 1975, 1,223 selections originating from various research stations were screened against gall midge (*Pachydiplosis oryzae*), and against rice tungro virus and its green leafhopper vector (*Nephotettix virescens* and *N. apicalis*) under high natural pressure. Screening was carried out at Chiplima, a hot spot for both rice tungro virus disease and gall midge. Entries were scored on the standard

0–9 scale. Gall midge incidence was heavy.

A high buildup of the green leafhopper was accompanied by epidemic rice tungro virus disease. Only 57 of the entries survived at 50 days after planting. On the 80th day after planting, 18 varieties seemed to promise multiple resistance to the pest and the disease (see table), and survived until harvest. Only one variety, designated 52094 (IR8/MTU10), showed immunity to gall midge; three varieties, RP974-210-10-8, CRM14-29-R-75, and IR2071-621-2-3, were highly tolerant of the rice tungro virus disease.

Another strain, designated as “T” strain, was reported from the Philippines by Rivera in 1970. This strain produces interveinal stripes on FK 135 but causes much less stunting than the “S” strain or even the “M” strain. The characteristic symptom of the “T” strain is the narrowing of leaves in rice cultivars TN1, IR5, IR8, and IR22.

Subsequent studies in India revealed the occurrence of five distinct strains of RTV, introducing complexity in strain differentiation and nomenclature. Shastry reported the occurrence of two strains in 1972 and designated them as RTV₁ and RTV₂. Anjaneyulu and John provided evidence of the existence of four RTV strains in India in 1972. They retained RTV₁ as such, divided RTV₂ into the two distinct strains of RTV_{2A} and RTV_{2B}, and designated a new strain as RTV₃. All four Indian strains behaved like the “S” strain on differentials used by Rivera and Ou in 1967, but were separable on the Indian set of differentials consisting of TN1, Pankhari 203, Ambemohar 102, Ambemohar 159, Kamod 253, and Latisail. Another Indian strain, designated as RTV₄, was detected and characterized by Mishra, Niazi, Basu, Ghosh, and Raychandhuri in 1976.

Rice varieties showing multiple resistance to gall midge (GM) and rice tungro virus disease (RTV) in national screening nursery at Regional Research Station, Chiptima, kharif 1975.

Designation	Cross	Reaction ^a to	
		GM	RTV
RP10-2	IR8/PTB10	3	3
RP633-9-5-8-1	(IR8/BJ1-43) × IR22	4	2
R2353	W1263/CR10-4011	3	4
JR mutant 2-25-4	Rexoro/R11	3	3
TNAU13610	Co Mutant	3	3
RP974-112-1-6	Sona/RP9-4	2	3
RP974-210-10-8	"	2	1
32343	W1263/Tella Hamsa	3	2
52094	IR8/MTU10	0	2
CRM14-29-R-75	W1263/SM1-6	3	1
RP825-71-4-9	Vijaya/PTB21	3	3
RP825-71-4-10	"	3	4
RP825-71-4-11	"	4	2
RP825-71-4-1	"	3	3
RP825-71-4-4	"	3	4
IR2071-875-2-3-4		2	4
IR2071-621-2-3		2	1
IR2071-747-6-3-2 (IR32)		2	4
<i>Susceptible checks:</i>			
for gall midge – Jaya		9	–
for RTV – TN1		–	9

^aEntries were scored for resistance on the standard 0–9 scale: 0–3 = good or high; 4–6 = fair or intermediate; 7–9 = poor or low.

A proposed key to the strains of rice tungro virus

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Since studies on the strains of rice tungro virus (RTV) began in 1967, eight strains have been reported from the Philippines and India. On the basis of the plant symptoms and the varietal reaction to

these strains, we propose a key to characterization of the strains.

In 1967, Rivera and Ou reported two strains of RTV which they designated as “S” and “M” strains. The two strains are differentiable on Acheh, FK 135, and Pacita, which respond to the “S” strain by developing symptoms of conspicuous interveinal chlorosis. The “M” strain produces mottling but not the yellowish stripes characteristic of the “S” strain. Further, the infection by the “S” strain causes much more stunting of FK 135 than does infection by the “M” strain.

A key to the strains of RTV (see figure) gives an idea of the latest position in this regard. The “T” strain and all the Indian strains have been grouped here under “S” strain on the basis of the reaction of FK 135.

Because of anomalies in nomenclature of the RTV strains, we propose the following modifications: Leaving the “M” strain as such, the various constituents of the “S” strain complex should be designated as “S” in numerical sequence. Accordingly, the strains presently known as “T”, RTV₁, RTV_{2A}, RTV_{2B}, RTV₃, and RTV₄ should be designated as S₁, S₂, S₃, S₄, S₅, and S₆, respectively. That would systematize the available information.

A more comprehensive treatment of the subject is not yet possible because the RTV strains in various countries have not yet been identified. The situation calls for immediate study of strain differentiation on a global scale with due care to